

Original article

Population-specific quantitative ultrasound reference ranges and nomogram for splenic parenchymal echotexture evaluation in children

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Abstract

Background: Sonographic assessment of spleen parenchymal echotexture in children remains largely subjective due to the absence of established population-specific quantitative reference criteria. Accurately detecting parenchymal anomalies in conditions such as sickle cell disease (SCD) requires objective normative data. Using quantitative mean pixel intensity (MPI) analysis, this study aimed to establish normative reference ranges and develop a clinical nomogram for the objective evaluation of spleen parenchymal echotexture in children. **Materials and Methods:** Standardised spleen ultrasonography was performed on 45 healthy Nigerian children, aged two to 14 years, as part of a cross-sectional study. Mean Pixel Intensity (MPI) was extracted from a manually positioned region of interest within the spleen parenchyma using a validated in-house developed MATLAB algorithm. SPSS version 23.0 was used for data analysis. One-way ANOVA was used to compare means across age groups. The 25th and 75th age-stratified normative percentiles were computed. Using an independent cohort of 45 children with sickle cell disease (SCD), a receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis established a diagnostic threshold for aberrant echotexture. **Results:** For healthy spleens, the mean pixel value of the parenchymal echotexture was 30.9 ± 12.9 , whereas for SCD subjects it was 63.47 ± 14.67 . The established normative reference ranges (25th-75th percentile) ranged from 22.8 to 40.1, with no statistical difference between age groups ($p = 0.54$). For SCD, the MPI showed outstanding diagnostic ability (AUC = 0.96). Sensitivity of 91.1% and specificity of 86.7% were obtained at the optimal threshold of 40.6. Age-based normative curves and the diagnostic threshold were combined to create a clinical nomogram. **Conclusion:** This study establishes the first population-specific quantitative ultrasound reference ranges along with a clinical nomogram for the objective assessment of splenic parenchymal echotexture in children. It demonstrates significant clinical utility for the early identification of splenic pathology in children suffering from sickle cell disease.

Keywords: Echotexture, Mean pixel intensity, Sickle Cell Disease, Spleen, Ultrasonography.

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Introduction

The spleen, the largest secondary lymphoid organ, performs a variety of immunologic tasks in addition to its roles in hematopoiesis and red blood cell clearance. Its physical structure enables it to remove infections and aberrant cells from the blood.¹ One of the first organs impacted by Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) is the spleen.² Early childhood splenic ischemia brought on by sickled cells eventually results in irreparable spleen damage.³ It is well known that hyposplenism is a major characteristic of SCD and that splenic function is lost during the first few years of life.^{4,5} The radiologic appearance of the spleen changes most often in SCD patients, likely as a result of vaso-occlusive events and the use of both acute or long-term transfusion therapy.⁶

From the embryonic stage through a person's life, ultrasound has been a vital medical imaging modality in modern diagnostics.^{7,8} This makes it possible to evaluate the health of several different organs^{7,8}. Compared with X-ray imaging, ultrasound offers several significant advantages: it provides extensive information for clinical diagnostics and real-time, dynamic images of organs and tissues in a radiation-free, cost-effective manner.⁹ Due to its non-ionising nature, accessibility, and real-time capabilities, ultrasound is the main imaging modality used to assess the spleen in pediatric populations.¹⁰ However, ultrasonic examination heavily depends on manual operation, in contrast to other medical imaging methods. High variability in inter-sonographer outcomes, especially among less-experienced sonographers, results from this substantial reliance on sonographer experience, which reduces test standardisation and accuracy.¹¹⁻¹³

Subjective descriptions of parenchymal echotexture, such as homogenous, heterogeneous, or coarse, are commonly used in clinical evaluation of the spleen. These descriptors are intrinsically variable and not repeatable among observers.¹⁴ A remedy for this subjectivity is provided by quantitative echotexture analysis, which uses grayscale images to extract objective measures such as mean pixel intensity.¹⁵ However, the lack of documented, population-specific normative reference values hinders the clinical application of such approaches. Determining whether a measured echotexture value falls within a normal range or shows early disease is difficult without these benchmarks.

This disparity is especially important in areas like sub-Saharan Africa, where spleen-related disorders, such as sickle cell disease (SCD), are highly prevalent.¹⁶ Clinical care could be informed by early diagnosis of splenic alterations, such as fibrosis, prior to autosplenectomy, but this requires sensitive and objective measurements. Thus, the purpose of this study was to: (1) use a quantitative pixel-intensity algorithm and establish normative reference ranges for spleen parenchymal echotexture in a cohort of healthy Nigerian children. (2) Create a useful clinical nomogram that integrates these normative data with a diagnostic threshold to help identify abnormal echotexture.

Materials and methods

Study Design and Participants

This was a cross-sectional study involving children diagnosed with sickle cell disease (SCD) alongside age-matched healthy controls. Ethical approval for

the research was granted by the institutional review board (Approval No: NREC/040/11/19B/2021/020). Written informed consent was secured from parents or guardians, and assent was obtained from children when appropriate before their participation. Subjects in the SCD group were recruited from the paediatrics clinic at the General Hospital Azare, located in North-Eastern Nigeria, between January and August, 2025. The inclusion criteria required a confirmed diagnosis of homozygous sickle cell disease (HbSS) through haemoglobin electrophoresis and a clinically stable (steady-state) condition at the time of data collection. Both male and female children attending routine follow-up visits were enrolled. For the control group, age-matched apparently healthy children with a normal haemoglobin genotype (HbAA), verified through hospital medical records, were recruited from the pediatric outpatient clinic. Subjects from both groups were excluded if they had any conditions known to impact splenic morphology or echotexture, including a history of splenic trauma or surgery, congenital or acquired splenic abnormalities (such as cysts, infarctions, lobulations, accessory spleen, or hemangioma), lymphadenopathy, or other systemic diseases affecting the spleen. Children presenting with current fever or a history of febrile illness within four weeks before examination, as well as those with any acute infection or inflammatory condition at the time of scanning, were also excluded. Additional exclusion criteria for the SCD group included evidence of autosplenectomy (non-visualisation of the spleen on ultrasound). In the control group, children diagnosed with sickle cell disease or any other hemoglobinopathy were excluded. Children whose parents or guardians did not provide consent or whose assent was not obtained were also excluded from the study.

Sample Size Estimation

The minimum number (n) of subjects needed for the study was calculated using Cochran's formula.¹⁷

$$n = Z^2 P (1-P) / d^2$$

Where:

Z = is the standard normal variant, which is 1.96 at 5% type 1 error ($p \leq 0.05$) and 2.58 at 1% type 1 error ($p \leq 0.01$). This study uses 1.96 because, as in most other studies, the p-value was deemed significant below 0.05.

P = is the predicted percentage in the population derived from pilot or prior research. However, SCD within the states in Nigeria ranges from 1%-3%.¹⁸ In this study, 3% considered the prevalence of SCD in Nigeria.

d = Absolute error or precision - the fixed percentage in this study is 5 per cent.

The smallest sample size is thus

$$N = 1.962 \times 0.03 (1-0.03) / 0.05^2 = 44.69 \approx 45$$

Therefore, 45 sickle cell disease subjects were recruited from the paediatrics clinic, and 45 non-sickle cell children were enrolled as the control group.

Ultrasound Image Acquisition

To reduce technical variability, a uniform sonographic methodology was used. All ultrasound examinations were conducted by a skilled Radiographer/sonographer possessing over 14 years of expertise in pediatric and abdominal ultrasonography, alongside a certified consultant radiologist with over 13 years of experience in abdominal imaging. Both professionals adhered to a standardised imaging protocol to guarantee uniformity in image acquisition among all subjects. The right lateral decubitus position was used for each subject. A Mindray DP10 ultrasound equipment with a curvilinear transducer (3.5–5 MHz) was used to image the spleen. Gain, depth, dynamic range, and time-gain compensation (TGC) were among the system parameters optimised at the beginning of the investigation and remained unchanged for all subsequent analysis. During suspended inspiration, a single longitudinal image that captured the maximum splenic length was obtained and stored for examination in an uncompressed DICOM file.

Quantitative Echotexture Analysis

The analysis was conducted utilising MATLAB R2022a (MathWorks Inc., Natick, MA, USA). The Mean Pixel Intensity (MPI) was determined as the average grayscale pixel value within the designated ROI on an 8-bit scale (0-255) employing standard image processing functions (imread, mean). In order to avoid vessels and artefacts, the user manually positioned a rectangular region of interest (ROI) inside a homogeneous area of the spleen parenchyma. As the major echotexture metric, the system determined the Mean Pixel Intensity (MPI) within the ROI (fig. 1). The Mean Pixel Intensity (MPI) measurement repeatability was carefully evaluated. A single trained operator re-measured the MPI from thirty randomly chosen images two weeks later in order to assess intra-observer variability. A second blinded operator estimated the MPI from the same 30 images separately in order to assess inter-observer variability. A two-way mixed-effects model called the Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) for absolute agreement was used to evaluate the agreement for

both intra- and inter-observer measures. Excellent reliability was deemed to be shown by an ICC value >0.90 . Before our measurement procedure was used with the entire population, our analysis verified its robustness.

Fig 1: Defined Region of Interest in spleen image

Statistical Analysis and Nomogram Development

Data were analysed using SPSS v23.0.

Reference Ranges: For the overall cohort as well as three age groups (<5, 5–9, and 10–14 years), descriptive statistics (mean, SD) for MPI were computed. One-way ANOVA was used to compare MPI across age categories. Normative bounds were established by calculating the 25th and 75th percentiles. The range from the 25th to the 75th percentile was selected to illustrate the interquartile normative band, thereby reducing the impact of outliers due to the limited sample size.

Diagnostic Threshold: The Mean Pixel Intensity (MPI) values from 45 children with SCD and 45 healthy controls were used in a ROC curve analysis to identify the ideal cut-off value for differentiating between normal and aberrant parenchyma. The threshold was chosen using the Youden Index.

Nomogram Construction: A nomogram with two axes was made. The healthy cohort percentile curves (25th and 75th) were used to plot age against MPI on the main axis. Percentile curves were created through linear interpolation among different age groups. The Receiver Operator Characteristic curve-derived diagnostic threshold is included on a secondary, parallel axis as a clear “abnormality line”. This enables a physician to plot a patient's MPI according to age and visually evaluate its location in relation to the pathological threshold and population percentiles.

Results

Participant Characteristics

The 45 healthy children range in age from 2–14 years, with 32 (71.1%) males and 13 (28.9%) females. Of the 45 SCD children, 26 (57.8%) were males, while 19 (42.2%) were females. Characteristics of the study subjects are shown in Table 1. Age categories of the healthy group are presented in Table 2:

Table 1: Characteristics of the study subjects

Parameter	Control subjects	Sickle cell subjects
No of subjects	45	45
Age Mean ± SD	9.8 ± 3.8	7.3 ± 3.3
Gender n (%)		
Male	32 (71.1%)	26 (57.8%)
Female	13 (28.9%)	19 (42.2%)
Weight (kg) (Mean ± SD)	17.9 ± 6.9	24.8 ± 7.6
Height (cm) (Mean ± SD)	104.9 ± 20.5	120.5 ± 17.1
BMI (kg/m ²) (Mean ± SD)	15.6 ± 1.4	20.9 ± 28.9

Table 2: Age categories of the healthy subject

Age Category (years)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Under 5	6	13.3
5-9	11	24.4
10-14	28	62.2
Total	45	100

Spleen parenchymal echotexture among the study subjects

The spleen parenchymal echotexture pixel value among the normal control subjects ranged from 7.4 to 59.6, with a mean of 30.9 ± 12.9. However, that of the sickle cell disease subjects ranged from 30.7 to 95.1, with a mean of 63.47 ± 14.67. The distribution was wide and statistically significant ($p = 0.001$).

Aged-Stratified Normative Reference Range Among Healthy Subjects

The overall mean MPI for healthy children's spleens was 30.9 ± 12.9. The distribution was wide, with values ranging from 7.4 to 59.6. The calculated reference intervals were: 25th Percentile: 22.8, 75th Percentile: 40.1. Age-stratified means and reference limits are presented in Table 3. No significant difference in MPI was found across age groups ($p=0.54$), indicating echotexture stability

Diagnostic Threshold from ROC Analysis

The ROC curve (Figure 2) for MPI showed excellent diagnostic performance in distinguishing SCD spleens from those of healthy controls. With an Area Under the Curve (AUC) of 0.96 ($p = 0.001$), the optimal cut-off value was 40.6, yielding a sensitivity of 91.1% and a specificity of 86.7%.

Figure 2: Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve for Mean Pixel Intensity (MPI) in differentiating sickle cell disease (SCD) from healthy spleens.

Reliability Assessment

The intra-observer reliability was found to be excellent (ICC = 0.94; 95% CI: 0.89-0.97), while the inter-observer reliability was similarly excellent (ICC = 0.92; 95% CI: 0.87-0.96).

The Clinical Nomogram

A clinical nomogram was created based on the aforementioned findings (Figure 3). A doctor can find the patient's age on the horizontal axis using the nomogram.
 2. Draw the predicted normal range (shaded zone between the 25th and 75th percentiles) by intersecting the percentile curves with a vertical line.
 3. Plot the measured MPI value for the patient.
 4. Immediately see whether the result is within the normal shaded zone or if it is higher than the "Abnormality Threshold" line, which is set at MPI = 40.6 and strongly indicates pathological parenchymal alteration.

Table 3: Age-Stratified Reference Ranges for Splenic Mean Pixel Intensity (MPI) in Healthy Children

Age Category (years)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Mean MPI (\pm SD)	25 th Percentile	75 th Percentile
Under 5	6	13.3	30.3 \pm 13.2	23.7	41.5
5-9	11	24.4	30.6 \pm 14.6	20.1	38.3
10-14	28	62.2	31.2 \pm 12.7	23.2	40.6
Total	45	100	30.9 \pm 12.9	22.8	40.1

Figure 3: Clinical nomogram for echotexture of splenic parenchyma in children. The shaded area shows the normative reference range, which falls between the 25th and 75th percentiles of Mean Pixel Intensity (MPI) based on data from healthy subjects. A dashed horizontal line marks the ROC-derived threshold for abnormality at MPI of 40.6. By plotting individual patient MPI values against age, clinicians can make quick, effective clinical interpretations.

Discussion

Using pixel intensity-based ultrasound analysis, this work establishes the first population-specific quantitative reference ranges and a clinically useful nomogram for spleen parenchymal echotexture in children. The study addresses a long-standing problem in pediatric spleen imaging by moving beyond subjective visual assessment, especially in regions such as Nigeria, where sickle cell disease (SCD) is more prevalent. As said, 1%-3% of Nigerians suffer from sickle cell Disease (SCD), the most prevalent hereditary condition.¹⁹

Subjective characteristics such as homogeneity, heterogeneity, or coarse echotexture, which are intrinsically operator-dependent and weakly repeatable, are a major component of conventional sonographic evaluation of the spleen¹⁴. In pediatric imaging, where small parenchymal alterations may precede morphologic problems, this subjectivity is particularly problematic. This study yielded a normative mean pixel intensity (MPI) of 30.9 \pm 12.9, providing clinicians with an objective benchmark to distinguish early pathogenic change from normal physiological variation. Although many studies

have concentrated on determining reference values for children's splenic length and volume²⁰⁻²⁷, these dimension measurements are more indicative of organ size than tissue integrity. Conversely, the underlying microstructural and acoustic characteristics of the spleen, such as fibrosis, congestion, and cellular infiltration, are reflected in echotexture.²⁸ Therefore, by providing a tissue-level quantitative metric that improves diagnostic sensitivity, our findings supplement current morphometric data.

The relative stability of splenic MPI throughout pediatric age groups is a significant finding in our investigation. The lack of substantial echotexture variation ($p = 0.54$) indicates that the acoustic nature of normal splenic parenchyma is constant throughout childhood, despite well-documented age-related increases in splenic size.²⁹ Because it encourages the use of a single reference framework with age-adjusted percentiles rather than completely distinct age-specific thresholds, this discovery streamlines clinical application. Organ dimensions, on the other hand, necessitate constant changes in body surface area, height, or age. Echotexture durability supports its potential as a reliable biomarker for long-term surveillance, especially in chronic hematologic disorders such as sickle cell disease (SCD), where parenchymal damage progresses over time.

The suggested echotexture metric was robustly validated by using SCD as a diseased model. Increased MPI consistently indicates abnormal spleen parenchyma, as indicated by ROC analysis, which showed high discriminative ability ($AUC = 0.96$). The potential of quantitative echotexture analysis as an early marker of splenic compromise is demonstrated by the obtained diagnostic threshold of $MPI = 40.6$, with sensitivity of 91.1% and specificity of 86.7%. Our validation aligns with several studies that use ROC to assess the effectiveness of their models.³⁰⁻³⁴

Long before the onset of autosplenectomy, repeated vaso-occlusive events in SCD cause ischemia, fibrosis, and a progressive loss of splenic function.³⁵ An important clinical benefit is the capacity to objectively identify such alterations before to permanent harm. Quantitative ultrasound provides a non-invasive, real-time approach to early risk classification, in contrast to test results or clinical history, which often reflect established dysfunction. The conversion of intricate quantitative data into a clinically understandable nomogram is a major breakthrough of this study. The nomogram enables quick visual interpretation during regular ultrasound exams by combining age-based

normative percentiles with a pathology-specific diagnostic threshold. This design fills the gap between routine clinical practice and research-grade image analysis. Crucially, the nomogram improves clinical judgment by offering objective numerical context rather than replacing it. In resource-constrained environments where advanced imaging modalities may not be readily accessible, a measured MPI that maps to the abnormality threshold provides standardised evidence to support diagnostic decisions, reduce inter-observer variability, and improve reporting consistency.

To our knowledge, there are no documented studies that have provided quantitative values for splenic echogenicity utilising the MPI technique. The majority of current ultrasound research in both pediatric and adult groups focuses on morphological dimensions or qualitative echotexture, rather than on objective measures of pixel intensity. For instance, Ladu et al. (2024) developed model-based reference ranges for splenic dimensions in normal controls from North-Eastern Nigeria and compared spleen size between patients with sickle cell disease and healthy children.³⁶ However, they did not present quantitative metrics such as mean pixel intensity (MPI) for the splenic parenchyma. Although the direct comparison of MPI values across studies is constrained by variations in imaging protocols, analysis software, and population characteristics. The MPI values recorded in our healthy pediatric cohort (mean \pm SD: 30.9 ± 12.9) are largely consistent with previously reported grayscale texture metrics from liver and renal studies involving similar pediatric cohorts.^{37,38} This indicates that our quantitative findings are within the anticipated biological ranges. Furthermore, our observation of significantly elevated MPI in SCD children corresponds with sonographic findings of increased echogenicity in organs impacted by chronic hemolytic disorders.³⁹ Future research employing standardised quantitative echotexture methodologies will be crucial for enabling direct comparisons across various populations and disease states.

The adoption of a consistent imaging technique, a verified in-house MATLAB algorithm, and a thorough evaluation of intra- and inter-observer reproducibility are some of this study's strong points. When a standardised ROI placement approach is used, the high ICC values indicate that MPI measurements are reliable and repeatable. However, there are a few limitations to consider. The accuracy of extreme percentile estimates may

be affected by the relatively small sample size, especially in younger age groups. To improve and externally validate these reference ranges, larger, multi-centre research is required. Cross-platform validation is crucial before widespread implementation, as ultrasound system-specificities also affect pixel-intensity values. Despite being repeatable, the manual ROI placement process is still somewhat subjective. To further improve objectivity and scalability, future research should concentrate on automated or semi-automatic segmentation methods. Lastly, although SCD was used as a validation model, further research is needed to determine whether the abnormality threshold can be applied to other splenic pathologies, such as lymphoma, portal hypertension, or infiltrative illnesses.

Conclusion

This research establishes quantitative ultrasound reference ranges specific to populations and a nomogram for splenic parenchymal echotexture in children and validates its diagnostic utility in sickle cell disease (SCD). This methodology provides an objective and reproducible framework for the early identification of splenic pathology and promotes standardised reporting in ultrasound examinations. Future research should confirm these reference ranges in larger multi-centre cohorts and investigate the integration with Doppler indices and automated segmentation methods.

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